

Synthesis, antitubercular and antimicrobial activity of some new *N*-aryl-1,4-dihydropyridines containing furan nucleus

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Abstract : A wide range of biological activities are associated with 1,4-dihydropyridines individually or in combination. The synthesis of *N*-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines (6a-j) and *N*-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines (7a-j) was under-taken with hope that they may be biologically active molecules with improved activity, less toxicity and undesirable side effects. The newly synthesized compounds were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. All newly synthesized compounds were tested for their antitubercular activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇RV ATCC 27294, antibacterial activity against different Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria and antifungal activity.

Keywords : *N*-Aryl-1,4-dihydropyridines, antitubercular activity, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Among a wide variety of heterocycles that have been explored for developing pharmaceutically important molecules. 1,4-Dihydropyridines possess a broad spectrum of biological activities, such as the ability to control the influx of calcium into cells, as well as enzymatic¹, antitubercular², antimicrobial^{3,4}, anti-hypertensive^{5,6} and many other properties. 4-Aryl-1,4-dihydropyridines for the nifedipine type (DHPs, e.g. 1-3) are the most studied class of organic calcium channel blockers⁷⁻⁹ and, since their introduction into clinical medicine in 1975, have become almost indispensable for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases such as hypertension, cardiac arrhythmias or angina¹⁰.

More than 30 years after the introduction of nifedipine 1, many DHP analogs have been synthesized and numerous second-generation commercial products have appeared on the market¹¹. A number of dihydropyridine calcium antagonists have been introduced as potential drugs for the treatment of congestive heart failure¹²⁻¹⁴. Further, cerebrotast, a dihydropyridine derivative, has been introduced as a neuroprotective agent¹⁵. A number of dihydropyridine derivatives have been found as vasodilators, bronchodilators, hepatoprotective, antitumour, antimitagenic, antidiabetic and antiplatelet aggregation agents¹⁶⁻²⁰. However, the potential of dihydropyridines as antitubercular and anti-microbial agents have not been

(1) Nifedipine

(2) (*R*)-Nilvadipine

(3) (*S*)-Felodipine

studied in broad spectrum. Therefore, the current study was undertaken to synthesize different dihydropyridine derivatives and investigate their antitubercular potential

using *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇RV and antibacterial potential using different Gram +ve bacteria *Bacillus megaterium* ATCC 14518, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 and Gram -ve bacteria *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 29213, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 9029. Our interest in the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines stems from their antitubercular and antimicrobial studies and interesting biological properties of several marine alkaloids^{21,22} based upon 1,4-dihydropyridines system.

The first synthesis of a 1,4-dihydropyridine (1,4-DHP) was reported by Arthur Hantzsch²³ in 1882 and is still the most common method for the preparation of these compounds. The classic Hantzsch reaction involves the combination of 1 equivalent of an aromatic aldehyde, 2 equivalents of a β -ketoester and 1 equivalent of ammonia in an alcoholic solvent at reflux to give the 1,4-DHP 4 (Scheme 1)²⁴.

The active methylene compound i.e. 1,3-dicarbonyl compound reacts with one mole of aryl aldehyde to give arylidene and one mole reacts with ammonia to give enamine compound. Michael addition of this results in the tautomeric system, which undergoes cyclization to the hydroxy tetrahydropyridine, followed by loss of water. The rate determining step is Michael addition.

Scheme 1. Possible intermediates in the Hantzsch reaction to form 1,4-DHPs.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of *N*-substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines.

Results and discussion

The reaction of diazonium salt and freshly distilled furfural give 5-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fluorophenyl)furfural 5. One pot cyclocondensation under the refluxing condition of methyl acetoacetate, different aryl amine and aldehydes 5 to yielded *N*-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fluorophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines 6a-j²⁵ while 5 on reaction with ethyl acetoacetate and different aryl amine to give *N*-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fluorophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines 7a-j in 50–55% yield (Scheme 2). The structures of newly synthesized compounds were unambiguously established from the analysis of their spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectra).

Antitubercular activity : The antitubercular evaluation of the compounds was carried out at Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition Co-ordination Facility (TAACF), USA. Primary screening of the compounds for antitubercular activity have been conducted at 6.25 μ g/ml towards *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv in BACTEC 12B medium using the BACTEC 460 radiometric system. The compounds demonstration at least >90% inhibitions in the primary screen have been compared with standard drug Rifampicin at 0.25 μ g/ml concentrations and it showed 98% inhibition. The activity of compounds 6c, 6g, 7e and 7j were observed moderate, whereas, compounds 6b, 6f, 7d and 7h were found to be non active. The data % inhibitions are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Antitubercular and antimicrobial screening results of compounds 6a-i, 7a-i

Compd.	R	% Inhibition Antitubercular activity	Zones of inhibition in mm				
			Antibacterial activity			Antifungal activity	
			<i>B. mega</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
6a	C ₆ H ₅ -	53	12	20	11	17	18
6b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	7	15	17	13	14	21
6c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	62	11	18	14	11	14
6d	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	27	17	16	11	23	13
6e	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	14	14	19	19	18	15
6f	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	9	14	13	14	20	14
6g	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	63	16	11	15	16	14
6h	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	14	14	17	11	14	16
6i	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	27	19	14	9	14	19
6j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	33	17	14	10	17	17
7a	C ₆ H ₅ -	15	14	15	13	16	12
7b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	12	13	21	9	21	16
7c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	23	12	14	21	15	17
7d	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	4	18	12	10	22	14
7e	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	61	15	15	17	10	23
7f	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	17	12	17	19	14	11
7g	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	25	11	16	18	19	21
7h	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	6	12	22	16	10	18
7i	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	22	14	13	12	12	14
7j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	59	10	18	20	14	13
Ampicillin		-	20	24	22	21	-
Amoxicillin		-	21	24	25	25	-
Norfloxacin		-	18	17	24	25	-
Benzyl penicillin		-	20	18	18	15	-
Greseofulvin		-	-	-	-	-	24
Rifampicin		98	-	-	-	-	-

Antimicrobial activity : Antimicrobial activity of all newly synthesized compounds was carried out by using cup plate agar diffusion method²⁶. The zone of inhibition of the bacterial growth were measured in millimeter and recorded in Table 1. Standard drugs like Ampicillin, Amoxicillin, Norfloxacin, Benzyl penicillin and Greseofulvin were used for the comparison purpose. From the result of antimicrobial activity it is observed that the compounds 6d, 6i, 6j and 7d were active against *Bacillus megaterium*, 6a, 6e, 7b and 7h shows good activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, 6e, 7c, 7f and 7j were active against *Proteus vulgaris*, 6d, 6f, 7b and 7d were active against *Escherichia coli* and 6b, 6i, 7e and 7g were active against *Aspergillus niger*.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400 instrument in KBr disc and only principal sharply defined peaks (cm⁻¹) are reported. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC-300 MHz FT NMR using TMS as internal standard, chemical shifts in δ, ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on a GCMS-QP2010 spectrophotometer. All the synthesized

compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on 0.2 mm silica gel F-252 (Merck) plates.

Preparation of 5-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fourophenyl)-2-furfural (5) : A mixture of *m*-chloro-*p*-fouroaniline (14.5 g, 0.01 mol), hydrochloric acid (15%, 60 ml) and water (90 ml) was heated to get a clear solution. The clear hydrochloride solution was cooled to 0 °C and diazotized with NaNO₂ solution (30%, 24 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered and to the filtrate, water (50 ml), freshly distilled furfural (11.1 ml, 0.1 mol) and aqueous cupric chloride (2.5 g in 10 ml of acetone) were added with stirring. The stirring was continued for 4 h. The separated solid was collected by filtration and crystallized from ethanol. Yield 70%, m.p. 156 °C.

General procedure for the synthesis of *N*-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines (6a-j) : A mixture of 5-(*m*-chloro-*p*-fourophenyl)furfural 5 (2.24 g, 0.01 mol), methyl acetoacetate (2.32 ml, 0.02 mol) and different aryl amines (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 8 h. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 h. The yellow

crystalline product so obtained was isolated and crystallized from ethanol afforded a pure analytical sample.

N-(*p*-Phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6a**): m.p. 125–126 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.01 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.48 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.19 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.52 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.50–7.88 (8H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1651 (C=O), 1622 (C=C), 1581, 1548, 1488, 1442, 1326, 1332, 1180, 1089 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 495 *m/z* (Found: C, 65.37; H, 4.65; N, 2.79. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₃ClFNO₅: C, 65.39; H, 4.67; N, 2.82%).

N-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6b**): m.p. 136–137 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.08 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.52 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.14 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.61 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.03 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.44–7.85 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1631 (C=O), 1587 (C=C), 1566, 1489, 1437, 1321, 1232, 1182 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 530 *m/z* (Found: C, 61.13; H, 4.15; N, 2.60. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂Cl₂FNO₅: C, 61.14; H, 4.18; N, 2.64%).

N-(*o*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6c**): m.p. 202–204 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.05 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.35 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.25 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.33–7.85 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1662 (C=O), 1589 (C=C), 1477, 1787, 1319, 1230, 1182, 1089, 1024, 700 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 530 *m/z* (Found: C, 61.12; H, 4.13; N, 2.59. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂Cl₂FNO₅: C, 61.14; H, 4.18; N, 2.64%).

N-(*m*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6d**): m.p. 174–175 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.01 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.51 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.24 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.67 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.11 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.32–7.74 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1654 (C=O), 1614 (C=C), 1589, 1491, 1444, 1328, 1226, 1161, 1026 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 530 *m/z* (Found: C, 61.12; H, 4.17; N, 2.62. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂Cl₂FNO₅: C, 61.14; H, 4.18; N, 2.64%).

N-(*p*-Anisyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6e**): m.p. 212–214 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.91 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.67 (6H, s, OCH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, *p*-

OCH₃), 5.22 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.27 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.25–7.78 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1668 (C=O), 1680 (C=C), 1581, 1489, 1446, 1227, 1165, 1047, 1012, 756 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 525 *m/z* (Found: C, 63.91; H, 4.77; N, 2.62. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₅ClFNO₆: C, 63.94; H, 4.79; N, 2.66%).

N-(*p*-Tolyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6f**): m.p. 163–165 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.03 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.11 (3H, s, *p*-CH₃), 3.59 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.14 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.86 (1H, d, *J* 3.0 Hz, furyl-H), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.50–7.96 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1676 (C=O), 1628 (C=C), 1584, 1552, 1478, 1436, 1322, 1228, 1179, 1079 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 509 *m/z* (Found: C, 65.93; H, 4.90; N, 2.71. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₅ClFNO₅: C, 65.95; H, 4.94; N, 2.75%).

N-(*p*-Flourophényl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6g**): m.p. 133–134 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.07 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.68 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.11 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.81 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.28 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.24–7.72 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1665 (C=O), 1572 (C=C), 1491, 1439, 1305, 1235, 1167, 1028 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 513 *m/z* (Found: C, 63.07; H, 4.28; N, 2.70. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂ClF₂NO₅: C, 63.10; H, 4.31; N, 2.73%).

N-(*p*-Bromophényl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6h**): m.p. 147–149 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.11 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.15 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.35–7.95 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1670 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1577, 1483, 1425, 1352, 1315, 1240, 1176, 1068 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 574 *m/z* (Found: C, 56.40; H, 3.83; N, 2.40. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂BrClFNO₅: C, 56.42; H, 3.86; N, 2.44%).

N-(*o*-Nitrophényl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophényl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6i**): m.p. 121–122 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.08 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.65 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.13 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.63 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.18 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.35–7.98 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1664 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1568, 1448, 1431, 1325, 1234, 1174, 1066 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 540 *m/z* (Found: C, 59.91; H, 4.08; N, 5.16. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂ClFN₂O: C, 59.95; H, 4.10; N, 5.18%).

N-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**6j**): m.p. 185–186 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.99 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.71 (6H, s, OCH₃), 5.07 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.24 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.48–8.02 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1662 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1569, 1491, 1431, 1323, 1234, 1176, 1020 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 540 *m/z* (Found: C, 59.93; H, 4.06; N, 5.14. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂ClFN₂O₇: C, 59.95; H, 4.10; N, 5.18%).

General procedure for the synthesis of N-aryl-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(m-chloro-p-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridines (7a-j): A mixture of 5-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)furfural **5** (2.24 g, 0.01 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (2.32 ml, 0.02 mol) and different aryl amines (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under refluxed condition for 8 h. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 h. The yellow crystalline product so obtained was isolated and crystallized from ethanol or suitable solvents.

N-(Phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7a**): m.p. 151–152 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.23 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.38 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.34 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.19 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.18 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.50–7.88 (8H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1670 (C=O), 1589 (C=C), 1569, 1485, 1429, 1225, 1170, 1089, 1012, 837 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 523 *m/z* (Found: C, 66.43; H, 5.17; N, 2.64. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₇ClFNO₅: C, 66.47; H, 5.19; N, 2.67%).

N-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7b**): m.p. 201–203 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.18 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.35 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.33 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.16 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.17 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.45–7.98 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1670 (C=O), 1628 (C=C), 1587, 1569, 1485, 1427, 1232, 1180, 1091 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 558 *m/z* (Found: C, 62.33; H, 4.65; N 2.49. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆Cl₂FNO₅: C, 62.37; H, 4.69; N, 2.51%).

N-(*o*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7c**): m.p. 222–223 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.20 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.36 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.35 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.18 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.21

(1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.56–7.89 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1672 (C=O), 1628 (C=C), 1587, 1548, 1485, 1427, 1232, 1180, 1091, 904, 776 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 558 *m/z* (Found: C, 62.33; H, 4.65; N 2.48. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆Cl₂FNO₅: C, 62.37; H, 4.69; N, 2.51%).

N-(*m*-Chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7d**): m.p. 184–185 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.25 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.37 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.39 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.14 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.12 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, furyl-H), 7.03 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, furyl-H), 7.45–7.98 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1587 (C=O), 1485, 1429, 1321, 1230, 1170, 1098, 1041 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 558 *m/z* (Found: C, 62.35; H, 4.64; N, 2.50. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆Cl₂FNO₅: C, 62.37; H, 4.69; N, 2.51%).

N-(*p*-Anisyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7e**): m.p. 226–227 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.27 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.39 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.68 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.41 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.21 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.27 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 3.7 Hz, furyl-H), 7.52–7.96 (8H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 627 (C=O), 1587 (C=C), 1569, 1481, 1423, 1232, 1180, 1091 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 554 *m/z* (Found: C, 65.01; H, 5.25; N 2.51. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₉ClFNO₆: C, 65.04; H, 5.28; N, 2.53%).

N-(*p*-Tolyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7f**): m.p. 153–155 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.19 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.22 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.51 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.31 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.15 (1H, s, CH_x-pyridine), 7.18 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.44–7.89 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1631 (C=O), 1587 (C=C), 1566, 1481, 1423, 1228, 1178, 1089, 921, 773 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 538 *m/z* (Found: C, 66.94; H, 5.41; N, 2.58. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₉ClFNO₅: C, 66.97; H, 5.43; N, 2.60%).

N-(*p*-Flourophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbomethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flourophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7g**): m.p. 157–158 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.25 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.38 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.37 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.15 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.18 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, furyl-H), 7.52–7.83 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1699 (CO) cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 541 *m/z* (Found: C, 64.23; H, 4.83; N, 2.55. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆ClF₂NO₅: C, 64.27; H, 4.84; N, 2.58%).

N-(*p*-Bromophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flouorophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7h**): m.p. 133–134 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.20 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.24 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.19 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.16 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.18 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.45–7.99 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1660 (C=O), 1587 (C=C), 1475, 1785, 1317, 1228, 1180, 1087, 1022, 698 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 602 *m/z* (Found: C, 57.73; H, 4.33; N, 2.29. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆BrClFNO₅: C, 57.77; H, 4.35; N, 2.32%).

N-(*o*-Nitrophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flouorophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7i**): m.p. 225–226 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.22 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.37 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.33 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.25 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.19 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.49–7.89 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1664 (C=O), 1624 (C=C), 1599, 1481, 1464, 1338, 1236, 1151, 1016 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 568 *m/z* (Found: C, 61.20; H, 4.60; N, 4.88. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆ClFN₂O₇: C, 61.22; H, 4.61; N, 4.92%).

N-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-dicarbethoxy-4-[5'-(*m*-chloro-*p*-flouorophenyl)-2'-furyl]-1,4-dihydropyridine (**7j**): m.p. 201–203 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.22 (6H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 2.37 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.19 (4H, q, CH₂-CH₃), 5.18 (1H, s, CH-pyridine), 7.23 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, furyl-H), 7.26 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, furyl-H), 7.52–7.78 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr): 1655 (C=O), 1612 (C=C), 1587, 1499, 1454, 1232, 1174, 1051, 1021, 753 cm⁻¹; MS (EI): 568 *m/z* (Found: C, 61.19; H, 4.59; N, 4.90. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆ClFN₂O₇: C, 61.22; H, 4.61; N, 4.92%).

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